

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY (ML) AND TERNARY (MAL) COMPLEXES IN 50% (V/V) ETHANOL—WATER MEDIUM

Temp = 30°, I = 0.1 M (KNO₃).

Cation	log K_{ML}^M	log $K_{ML_2}^{ML}$	log $K_{M-dipy-L}^{M-dipy-L}$	log $K_{M-o-phen-L}^{M-o-phen-L}$	$\Delta \log K_M$ L = o-phen(dipy)
Cu ²⁺	6.65	4.60	6.60	6.50	-0.15 (-0.05)
Ni ²⁺	4.70	3.38	4.44	4.31	-0.39 (-0.26)
Co ²⁺	4.53	3.48	4.11	4.11	-0.42 (-0.42)

pK_{OH}, 9.13; pK_{NH+}, 6.58.

plex decomposes and seems to form the metal hydroxides that precipitate out. Metal-dipy-SAP and metal-dipy curves overlap at low pH which shows that combination of the secondary ligand does not take place in the pH range where metal-primary ligand combination takes place. Mixed-ligand titration curve (b) diverges from the secondary ligand titration curve (a) at a pH above the complete formation of 1:1 metal-dipy complex and below the commencement of hydroxo-complex formation. Further, in the titration of the mixed-ligand system (curve b) no precipitate appears even after pH ≈ 9 and this indicates the formation of mixed-ligand complex. It may be assumed that the secondary ligand (SAP) would combine with metal-dipy complex species in ternary system just as it does with [M(H₂O)_n]²⁺ in the simple system. Similar observations have also been made when o-phenanthroline was used as the primary ligand instead of dipyrindyl. The values of log K_{MAL}^{MAL} have been determined using (i) half $\bar{n}$ -method and (ii) pointwise calculation method⁴. The two values agree closely, and the mean of these two values is given in Table 1.

Unlike our earlier observation⁵, it is found that in the present case log $K_{ML}^M \approx \log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$ (A = dipy or o-phen). The two nitrogen atoms of the dipyrindyl (o-phenanthroline) molecule besides forming σ-bonds with the metal ions, participate in M→L (dπ-pπ) interaction⁶. Due to this back-donation the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in [M(dipy)]²⁺ can not increase significantly and hence the tendency of [M(aq)]²⁺ or [M(dipy)]²⁺ to receive the secondary ligand remains nearly the same and this justifies log $K_{ML}^M \approx \log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$. The lower value of log $K_{ML_2}^{ML}$ than log K_{MAL}^{MAL} is however expected on the basis of coulombic repulsions⁶ exerted between the secondary ligand anions. For 1:1:1 mixed ligand complexes, the observed order of stability, Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ is the same as for the corresponding M-L systems. The plot of log K_{MAL}^{MAL} against log K_{ML}^M is a straight line suggesting⁷ that addition of the secondary ligand (L) to the (metal-dipy/o-phen) species follows the same trend as in the association of L to M²⁺(aq) ions in the binary system. The Δlog K values⁸ are negative (Table 1) Similar Δlog K values of mixed chelates involving

2,2'-dipyrindyl and "mixed donor" O-N atoms were obtained by Griesser and Sigel⁹.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N.N.G.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
- M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 3271.
- C. R. BERA and G. P. SEN GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 546.
- K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1011, 1027.
- G. P. SEN GUPTA and N. N. GHOSH *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 689.
- G. A. L'HEUREUX and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 481.
- B. K. AGRAWAL, K. DWIVEDI, M. CHANDRA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 931.
- H. SIGEL, *Chimia*, 1967, 21, 489.
- R. GRIESSER and H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 1238.

Polarographic Study of the Formation of Ternary Complexes of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) with Oxalate, Citrate, Salicylate or Benzoate and Pyruvate

MAHMOUD A GHANDOUR

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science (Assiut), Assiut University

and

HESHAM MANSOUR*, MOUSTAFA H. M. ABU EL-WAFA and MAHMOUD KHODARY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science at Qena, Qena, Egypt

Manuscript received 17 March 1988, revised 28 June 1988, accepted 6 July 1988

THE paper describes the possibility of the formation of ternary complexes of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with oxalate, citrate, salicylate or benzoate as primary ligand and pyruvate as the secondary ligand using polarographic technique.

Experimental

Polarograms were recorded with a Sargent-Welch XVI polarograph using SCE as the reference electrode and a DME. The dropping mercury electrode (DME) had the following characteristics: $m=1.76 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=4.3 \text{ s}$ in 0.1 M KCl solution (open circuit) at mercury height=60 cm, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=1.84 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$. The temperature of the cell was maintained at 30°.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and were dissolved in double-distilled water. Triton X-100 was used as the maximum suppressor and 1.0 M NaClO₄ as the supporting electrolyte. The polarograms were recorded after deaeration of the test solutions with purified nitrogen at 30°.

Results and Discussion

Cd²⁺-ligand systems: The half-wave potentials of Cd²⁺ shifted to more negative values on increasing the free ligand concentration. Since the plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs log (free ligand) were straight lines with breaks in the case of salicylate, the method of Lingane¹ was used to calculate the stability constants. On the other hand, the $-E_{1/2}$ vs log (free ligand) plots in the case of pyruvate, oxalate and citrate were smooth curves, and the method of DeFord and Hume² was followed to calculate the overall stability constants. The observed values of stability constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cd²⁺ BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES

Binary system	log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃
Cd ²⁺ - pyruvate	0.778	1.176	1.43
Cd ²⁺ - oxalate	2.477	3.903	5.04
Cd ²⁺ - citrate	1.95	3.30	-
Cd ²⁺ - salicylate	1.46	2.23	-
Ternary system	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
Cd ²⁺ (Ox)(Pyr)	3.15	3.154	4.00
			3.87
Cd ²⁺ (Cit)(Pyr)	-	3.787	5.61
Cd ²⁺ (Sali)(Pyr)	2.454	-	3.66
			3.36

It is clear from Table 1 that the previous values³⁻⁵ agree well with some of the present values and differ with the others, which may be due to the variation in the experimental conditions.

Polarograms were taken with solution containing fixed concentration of pyruvate and varying concentration of oxalate, citrate or salicylate. pH was kept at 6. All the reduction waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled.

The shift in half-wave potential to more negative side with increase in primary ligand concentrations (oxalate, citrate and salicylate) was observed. A

shift in the half-wave potential at a given concentration of both the ligands to more negative value than that for either of the simple systems at the same metal concentration, indicates the formation of mixed ligand complexes. Several equilibria exist, hence the DeFord and Hume² expression for F₀(X) may be extended to give a new function, F₀₀(X, Y) given by

$$F_{00}(X, Y) = \text{antilog} \left(\frac{-0.435 nF}{RT} E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_0} \right) = A + B[X] + C[X]^2 + D[X]^3$$

where, $A = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01}[Y] + \beta_{02}[Y]^2 + \beta_{03}[Y]^3$; $B = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[Y] + \beta_{12}[Y]^2$; $C = \beta_{20} + \beta_{21}[Y]$; $D = \beta_{30}$, the β_{i,j} values being the overall stability constants of the system (for simple complexes, i or j=0).

The values of all the stability constants in the above equations can be obtained if the half-wave potentials and diffusion currents of Y (pyruvate in this case) and increasing concentration of X (oxalate, citrate or salicylate) are measured. The formation constants of the binary complexes are already determined. The constants B, C and D can be obtained from the functions,

$$F_{10} = \frac{F_{00} - A}{[X]} = B + C[X] + D[X]^2$$

$$F_{20} = \frac{F_{10} - B}{[X]} = C + D[X]$$

$$F_{30} = \frac{F_{20} - C}{[X]} = D$$

by an extrapolation to zero ligand concentration of the graphical plots of the corresponding functions. The constant A can be obtained in the same way from F₀₀ or from the stability constants of Cd²⁺-pyruvate system. The same is true for the constant D, i.e. from the F₃₀ vs X plot, where D=β₃₀.

Cd²⁺ ligand - pyruvate systems: All the investigated systems were polarographed in the presence of 0.25 mM Cd²⁺, fixed concentration of pyruvate and varying concentrations of the primary ligand. In each case, the single well-defined wave had a slope of 31 ± 2 mV for the plot of $-E_{d,0}$ vs log $i(i_d - i)$, indicating that the reduction is reversible involving two electrons. The direct proportionality of the diffusion current to the effective height of mercury column indicates that the solution is entirely diffusion-controlled.

A shift in E_{1/2} potential to more negative side with the increasing primary ligand was observed. This shift is greater than that obtained in absence of pyruvate (secondary ligand). This indicates the formation of mixed complexes. The F₁₀ function

for $Cd^{II}(Ox)_i(Pyr)_j$ is represented by plots shown in Fig. 1. The values of β_{ij} are cited in Table 1. Since the values of β_{11} and β_{12} in the presence of citrate and salicylate respectively are negative, one can presume the absence of the corresponding complexes in the reaction mixture.

Fig. 1. Plots of F_{i0} vs Ox for $Cd^{II}(Ox)(Pyr)$ system at $[Pyr]=0.4 M$.

Following the procedures of Watters and Dewitt⁶, the predicted values for $Cd(Ox)(Pyr)$, $Cd(Ox)_2(Pyr)_2$ and $Cd(Ox)_3(Pyr)_2$ are $10^{2.93}$, $10^{2.64}$ and $10^{2.55}$, respectively, where the corresponding experimental values are $10^{3.15}$, $10^{2.15}$ and $10^{2.94}$ (mean value). The experimental values are higher than the predicted values for electrostatic and steric reasons^{6,7}; the enhancement is $10^{0.22}$, $10^{0.51}$ and $10^{0.39}$, respectively. In case of citrate the predicted value of $Cd(Cit)_2(Pyr)$ is $10^{2.15}$ the experimental being $10^{2.45}$ (mean value), and the enhancement is $10^{0.3}$. Finally, in the salicylate complexes, in presence of pyruvate, the predicted value is $10^{2.44}$ where the experimental value is $10^{2.51}$ (mean value) and the enhancement being $10^{1.07}$.

The various complexation reactions of $Cd(Ox)_i(Pyr)_j$ system may be represented as

Pb^{II} ligand systems: The reduction of 0.25 mM Pb^{II} in the presence of pyruvate, oxalate citrate or benzoate was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. From the plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs log (free ligand) straight lines were obtained with breaks. Lingane¹ method was used to calculate the stability constant values (Table 2). The present values are in a good agreement with those obtained by other workers⁸⁻¹⁰.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Pb^{II} BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES

Binary system	log β_1^2	log β_2^2	log β_3
Pb ^{II} - pyruvate	1.96	3.30	—
Pb ^{II} - oxalate	3.30	5.76	—
Pb ^{II} - citrate	3.86	5.08	—
Pb ^{II} - benzoate	2.08	3.46	—
Ternary system	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
Pb ^{II} (Ox)(Pyr)	2.19	3.77	—
Pb ^{II} (Cit)(Pyr)	4.91	—	6.52, 5.87
Pb ^{II} (Benzoate)(Pyr)	3.49	3.17	3.73, 4.303

Fig. 2. Distribution curves of the different complexes formed in the Cd^{II} -Oxalate-Pyruvate system in presence of 0.4 M pyruvate: (1) Cd^{II} , (2) $Cd(Pyr)_2$, (3) $Cd(Pyr)$ or $Cd(Pyr)_2$, (4) $Cd(Ox)_2(Pyr)$, (5) $Cd(Ox)(Pyr)_2$, (6) $Cd(Ox)$, (7) $Cd(Ox)(Pyr)$, (8) $Cd(Ox)_2$ and (9) $Cd(Ox)_3$.

As with Cd^{2+} , the polarograms were recorded with Pb^{2+} solution containing fixed concentration of pyruvate and varying concentration of oxalate, citrate or benzoate at pH 6. All the reduction waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled.

Shaap and McMasters⁷ method was used to calculate the values of A, B, C and β_{ij} ; (Table 2). It is difficult to calculate the predicted values of β_{ij} because we do not have the value of β_{so} or β_{os} for the simple complexes.

The distribution of different complexes formed in each system was calculated. As a representative, the distribution of $Cd(Ox)_i(Pyr)_j$ complexes (α %) as a function of oxalate concentration at $[Pyr]=0.04 M$ is shown in Fig. 2.

References

1. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 1.
2. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUMB, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5323.
3. T. ONCSCU and M. MACORSCHI, *An. Univ. Bucuresti., Ser. Stiint. Natur. Chim.*, 1967, 66, 77.
4. E. CAMPI, G. OSTACOLI, M. MEIRONE and G. SAINI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 553.
5. D. G. DHULEY, D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 2135.
6. J. I. WATTERS and R. DEWITT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1333.
7. W. B. SHAAP and D. L. McMASTERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
8. M. M. PALRECHA and J. N. GAUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 1035.
9. L. N. KLATT, *Anal. Chem.*, 1970, 42, 1837.
10. D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 503.

pH-metric Studies of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cadmium-, Magnesium-, Strontium- and Calcium-(II) with Pyruvate and Oxalate or Citrate

MAHMOUD A. GHANDOUR

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science,
Assiut University
and

HESHAM MANSOUR*, MOUSTAFA H. M.
ABU EL-WAFA and MAHMOUD KHODARY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science at Qena,
Qena, Egypt

Manuscript received 6 April 1988, accepted 8 July 1988

THE metal complexes of pyruvate are important due to the essential biological role of pyruvic acid, consequently the mixed-ligand complexes containing pyruvic acid acquires a special consideration. In the present paper aims to study the ternary system of the type MAL, where $M=Cd^{2+}, Sr^{2+}, Ca^{2+}$ or Mg^{2+} , A=primary ligand (oxalic or citric); L=secondary ligand (pyruvic).

Experimental

Calvin – Bjerrum’s technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹ was used to determine the protonation constants and the binary and the mixed formation constants of the complexes. pH measurements were carried out on a Orion 601 pH-meter. Oxygen was removed by bubbling pure nitrogen during titrations. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and all the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The titrations were carried out at 30°. Ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at 1.0 M NaClO₄.

Results and Discussion

Proton – ligand stability constants : The protonation constants of the ligands (pyruvic HL, oxalic H₂L, citric H₃L) were determined using equation (1),

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \frac{(V_2 - V_1)(N^0 + E^0)}{(V_0 + V_1)T_{L^0}} \quad (1)$$

where, $\bar{n}_A$ is the average number of protons attached per ligand, Y the displaceable hydrogen atoms, E^0 and T_{L^0} are the initial concentrations of the mineral acid and the ligand, respectively, V_1 and V_2 the volumes of alkali of normality N^0 required for the acid and the ligand titrations, respectively, at a given pH value and V_0 is the initial volume of the solution which is 25 ml in each case.

Formation curves are obtained by plotting values of $\bar{n}_A$ vs pH of the system. Values of pK_1^H for pyruvic acid, pK_1^H for oxalic acid and pK_1^H, pK_2^H and pK_3^H for citric acid are estimated by noting the pH at which $\bar{n}_A=0.5, 1.5$ and 2.5, respectively. The values along with the values reported in literature are given in Table 1.

Metal-ligand stability constant :

Pyruvate – metal complexes : The complex formation between pyruvate and some metal ions, viz. $Cd^{2+}, Mg^{2+}, Sr^{2+}$ and Ca^{2+} is indicated by the shift of metal – ligand titration curve from the ligand titration curve (Fig. 1 for Mg^{2+}). $\bar{n}$ (metal – ligand formation number) is obtained using expression (2),

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V_3 - V_2)(N^0 + E^0) + T_{L^0}(Y - \bar{n}_A)}{(V_0 + V_1)T_{M^0}\bar{n}_A} \quad (2)$$

where, V_2 and V_3 are the volumes of alkali required for the metal complex and the ligand titrations, respectively, at a given pH and T_{M^0} is the total concentration of metal ion (0.01 M). The remaining quantities have the same significance as given in equation (1). The metal – ligand stability constants were obtained from the curve drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL. Values of $pL = -\log [L]$, where $[L]$ is the free ligand concentration, are calculated using equation (3),